

Numerical Modelling of High-performance Fabrics with Emphasis on Rate-Dependency and Progressive Damage Failure Using Mechano-rheological Constitutive Models

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Abstract: Soft armour consisting of multi-layered high-performance fabrics are a popular choice for personal protection and is a crucial element in safeguarding military personnel in modern warfare. As such, extensive research, both numerical and experimental has been carried out to improve and optimise the performance of such materials. Especially, numerical modelling has proven to be a useful tool in capturing the kinetics of highly dynamic events such as ballistic impact. However, the numerical modelling process must be carefully manoeuvred and sufficiently validated, since improper inputs and problem definition will yield misleading outputs. When modelling a material, the behaviour of the material must be captured adequately by the constitutive material model in the finite element package to obtain comparable results. Probably the most common approach in modelling ballistic impact-resistant fabrics is to assign them an orthotropic or a transversely isotropic constitutive model. Consequently, the rate-dependent properties of materials such as *p*-Aramids and UHMWPEs remain largely unaddressed in most numerical simulations. Furthermore, element deletion based on critical stress levels is abrupt and consequently, the progressive damage yarns undergo is also unaccounted for. This paper aims to characterise the rate-dependent properties of such materials in finite element frameworks and to implement progressive damage failure regimes on constitutive models. The case of assigning a viscoelastic constitutive material model using rheological elements in LS-DYNA, using user-defined material subroutines is presented herein.

Keywords: ballistic impact, constitutive modelling, LS-DYNA, user-defined material model, viscoelastic.

1 Introduction

High-performance woven fabrics made of high-performance textile fibres such as aramids and Ultra-High Molecular Weight Polyethylene (UHMWPE) in a multi-layered arrangement has become a popular choice for lightweight personal body armour [1], [2]. Textile fibres are viscoelastic in nature [3], [4] and multi-layered arrangements of elastic and viscoelastic materials may be assembled to mitigate pressure and impulse on a system. In achieving the general objectives of body armour research, to produce low-cost, lightweight and comfortable armour systems while preserving superior ballistic performance against various threat levels [5], the design optimisation can be seen to be approached empirically rather than numerically. However, the complexity of destructive and high-speed testing makes it challenging to fully understand the dynamics of this process. Therefore, a purely empirical assessment, although useful, may not be ideal for studying the ballistic impact of fabrics.

Numerical modelling has gained popularity recently, in the design and optimization of armour materials. However, the numerical modelling process must be carefully manoeuvred and sufficiently validated, since improper inputs and problem definition will yield misleading outputs. Lately, it has become the case that numerical results be matched with experimental results, however possible, by tweaking material, contact or other parameters in the finite element code. Consequently, proper attention is not paid towards the constitutive material behaviour, which governs the numerical outputs. One such example is the case of high-performance fabrics used in armour. Even though it has been established that the stress-strain behaviour of fibres such as para-aramids (Kevlar and Twaron) are in fact, rate-dependant [6], [7] over a considerable range of strain rates, most numerical simulations employ rate-independent orthotropic elastic constitutive models [8]–[10]. Moreover, some numerical models use contradicting values for the same numerical model of some fabrics.

In LS-DYNA, an orthotropic elastic constitutive model can be assigned to a model by employing the material card *MAT_002_ORTHOTROPIC_ELASTIC, and is probably the most commonly used material card in simulating high-performance fabrics. Generally, the moduli in the transverse directions are taken

to be two-orders of magnitude smaller than the yarn axial direction while the Poisson ratio are taken to be zero [11]. Zero (or nearly zero) values are assigned in order to avoid numerical instabilities. This is one of the most common assumptions to be seen in using this material model in finite element simulations on fabric materials. However, such assumptions have serious adverse consequences in terms of the fundamental material response. When tensile (or compressive) loads are imparted on the homogenised yarn model, the yarn cross-section has to decrease artificially as a consequent of the assigned zero Poisson ratios [12]. Consequently, the stresses induced in such elements are higher than the actual stresses that should have been imposed. As a result, when element deletion based on *MAT_ADD_EROSION is enforced on *MAT_002, such elements will be deleted from the system, causing probable premature failure of yarns. *MAT_ADD_EROSION can enforce single or multiple failure criteria at the same time. These failure criteria include, but are not limited to; principle stress-, von-Mises stress-, strain- and pressure-based failure criteria. LS-DYNA now supports more sophisticated failure algorithms such as *MAT_ADD_DAMAGE_DIEM, *MAT_ADD_DAMAGE_GISSMO and *MAT_ADD_GENERALIZED_DAMAGE [13], however, these failure algorithms are more focused on metal-related problems. Viscoelastic models (*MAT_076_GENERAL VISCOELSTIC) are available in LS-DYNA for rate-dependent models. However, it is based on the generalised Maxwell model, having up to 18 terms in the Prony series expansion and is primarily for modelling dense continuum rubbers and solid explosives [13]. Moreover, the model does not accompany material failure, similar to *MAT_002. Micro-mechanical fabric constitutive models are also available (*MAT_214_DRY_FABRIC) in LS-DYNA with advanced features. However, its usage is limited to shell elements only and is a major constraint since solid elements are now preferred over shell, to capture intricate contact interactions in a fabric undergoing dynamic events [13].

In order to address the highlighted issues and to accommodate the rate-dependent properties, Shim *et al* [14], used the spring-dashpot constitutive models proposed by Roylance [15]. Shim *et al* [16] concluded that by using such a constitutive rate-dependant model, a better energy absorption prediction is obtained than a rate-independent model. Roylance [15] further emphasised that that viscoelastic relaxation gave rise to slower transverse shock wave propagation and a larger angle between the line of impact and the deflected yarn than a rate-independent model.

It is possible to define customised constitutive material models, with (optional) failure in LS DYNA, rather than using the common orthotropic elastic model which gives rise to serious deviations of material response. Such material definitions are called user-defined material subroutines (UMATs) and are one of the most advanced features of LS-DYNA. Generating a UMAT is complicated and demands comprehensive understanding of both solid mechanics and FORTRAN programming. UMATs are realised by *MAT_041-050 USER_DEFINED_MATERIAL_MODELS card in the LS-DYNA keyword deck. The governing constitutive equations can be input by the user as a FORTRAN subroutine, compiled into an executable solver for LS-DYNA. LS-DYNA is a finite element code written in FORTRAN. For explicit finite element analyses, nodal accelerations are solved directly using the net nodal force vector and the mass matrix. Subsequent to calculating the nodal accelerations for the n^{th} timestep, LS-DYNA then calculates nodal velocities and displacements at $n+1/2^{\text{th}}$ and $n+1^{\text{th}}$ timesteps, respectively [17]. From these nodal displacements, the strain tensor is populated and the corresponding material model which is responsible for linking the strain tensor with the stress tensor, as a constitutive equation/s is called by LS-DYNA. Instead of the built-in material models, a UMAT can be called for this purpose, by the main program.

The following outlines the population of a viscoelastic constitutive model using LS-DYNA UMATs to capture the rate-dependent properties of a rate-dependent fibre. Viscoelastic constitutive model suggested by Tapie *et al* [18] is taken as a case study to compare orthotropic elastic material in LS-DYNA with the rheological element-based viscoelastic model. Progressive damage failure of yarn materials suggested by Tapie *et al* [18] is also implemented and discussed.

2 Constitutive Model Development and UMAT Implementation

2.1 Constitutive Spring-dashpot Model

Fibres used for the production of ballistic fabrics are generally, polymers with highly-oriented polymer chains. Primary and secondary chemical bonds, polymer chain length among other factors govern the fracture of such materials. Figure 1 illustrates the possibility of denoting primary bonds along polymer chains and secondary (weaker) bonds among polymer chains in Twaron fibres [6]. Shim *et al* [6] used springs with stiffnesses K_1 and K_2 to account for these bonds in their finite element models. A dashpot

was employed to account for the viscous effects generated by slipping and sliding of polymer chains relative to each other. The assembly of these three rheological elements yielded the Zener viscoelastic model for that specific Twaron fibre variant. Similarly, depending on the morphology of any rate-dependant fibre type, spring and dashpot elements can be assembled in different configurations to yield a material response resembling the polymer of interest.

Figure 1: Illustration of primary and secondary bonds in Twaron fibre polymer chains [6]

Figure 2 illustrates the spring-dashpot combination used to characterise the constitutive behaviour of Twaron T1040 yarns.

Figure 2: Spring-dashpot model [18]

The first and second branches of the rheological model in Figure 2 depict Maxwell models with spring stiffnesses and viscous coefficients E_3 , E_2 , μ_3 and μ_2 , respectively. In each branch, the serial connections of springs and dashpots result in equal stress in either element in the branch while the total strain the branch undergoes is equal to the sum of the strains underwent by each element separately. For each Maxwell model, let σ_{tot} , σ_s and σ_d be the total stress in the branch, stress in the spring and the stress in the dashpot. Let ϵ_{tot} , ϵ_s and ϵ_d be the corresponding strains. Then, the following stress-strain relationships (1), (2) and (3) can be established for a Maxwell viscoelastic model.

$$\sigma_{tot} = \sigma_s = \sigma_d \quad (1)$$

$$\epsilon_{tot} = \epsilon_s + \epsilon_e \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{\epsilon}_{tot} = \dot{\epsilon}_s + \dot{\epsilon}_e \quad (3)$$

Where $\dot{\epsilon}$ refers to the rate of change of strain. The stress-strain relationships for springs and dashpots are given by (4) and (5), where E and μ denote the spring stiffness and dashpot constant, respectively.

$$\sigma_s = E \epsilon_s \quad (4)$$

$$\sigma_d = \mu \frac{d\epsilon}{dt} \quad (5)$$

Substituting (1), (2), (4) and (5) in (3) and solving the first order differential equation yields (6).

$$\sigma = \mu \dot{\epsilon} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{E\epsilon}{\mu \dot{\epsilon}}} \right) \quad (6)$$

For the viscoelastic model in Figure 2, the total stress is equal to the sum of stresses in each branch and the strain is equal for all three branches. Applying the result from (6) to the two branches yields (7) as the constitutive stress-strain relationship for the model illustrated in Figure 2. Equation (7) can be used to implement a FORTRAN subroutine to the main LS-DYNA program as a UMAT describing the viscoelastic behaviour of Twaron T1040 yarns.

$$\sigma = E_1 \varepsilon + \mu_2 \dot{\varepsilon} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{E_2 \varepsilon}{\mu_2 \dot{\varepsilon}}} \right) + \mu_3 \dot{\varepsilon} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{E_3 \varepsilon}{\mu_3 \dot{\varepsilon}}} \right) \quad (7)$$

The model constants E_1 , E_2 , E_3 , μ_2 , and μ_3 can be determined by fitting Equations (7) and (8) to experimental data. Equation (8) is obtained by differentiating (7) with respect to ε , which resembles the modulus at a given time 't'.

$$E = \frac{d\sigma}{d\varepsilon} = E_1 + E_2 e^{-\frac{E_2 \varepsilon}{\mu_2 \dot{\varepsilon}}} + E_3 e^{-\frac{E_3 \varepsilon}{\mu_3 \dot{\varepsilon}}} \quad (8)$$

2.2 UMAT Implementation

The simplified pseudo code for the UMAT implemented as the FORTRAN subroutine is shown below. The failure criterion used is stress-based and is based on the J2 flow theory/von-Mises failure criterion. The theory postulates that a material starts yielding when the second invariant of the deviatoric stress reaches a critical value and is calculated in the subroutine according to Equation (9).

$$\sigma_{vm} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} [(\sigma_1 - \sigma_2)^2 + (\sigma_2 - \sigma_3)^2 + (\sigma_1 - \sigma_3)^2]} \quad (9)$$

σ_{vm} in the pseudo code refers to the von-Mises stress calculated by the principal stress components of the stress tensor and is denoted by σ_{vm} in (9). UTS refers to the ultimate tensile strength of the yarns.

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SUBROUTINE umat41(*)
GET model constants Ei, Ui, UTS, Dmaximum, n, Eminimum
COMPUTE strain rates
IF vmises < UTS THEN
  COMPUTE stress tensor using Equation (7)
  INITIALISE additional history variables
ELSE IF vmises >= UTS THEN
  INITIALISE damage variable to 1
  CHECK if stress is sustained for 'n' timesteps
  IF sustained THEN
    REDUCE stiffness of the element
    IF stiffness =< Eminimum THEN
      DELETE element
    END IF
  END IF
ELSE
  WRITE "ERROR!"
END IF
END

```

A separate function was written for the subroutine to check for the von-Mises stress from the principal stress tensor components. When the pre-defined critical stress level-UTS is reached, a damage variable is set to one, and is increased with each timestep. However, before increasing the damage variable, the program checks if the stress is sustained in the element for a pre-defined number of timesteps as suggested by Tapie *et al* [18]. This approach avoids spurious element deletion/damage due to numerical noise. Subsequently, the stiffness of the element starts to degrade iteratively as shown by Equation (10) [18]. When the stiffness falls below a pre-specified value, the element is considered failed by the program and is deleted from the calculation. This is realised by setting the global logical variable 'failel' to .true. within the subroutine [17].

$$E_{n+1} = E_n \left(1 - \frac{D}{D_{maximum}} \right) \quad (10)$$

2.3 Numerical Model of the Fabric

In addition to the issue addressed above, another challenge that is largely unaddressed is modelling the relatively negligible flexural stiffness of yarns/fabrics. When a relatively high tensile modulus is assigned to yarn/fabric materials, this results in unrealistic, excessively high flexural stiffness when multiple solid elements are used through the thickness. Similarly, having multiple integration points through the thickness also endows the yarn/fabric with a high flexural stiffness. Only one solid element through the

thickness was used in the yarn mesh in this study. This approach, while reducing the flexural rigidity, also curtails computational cost by reducing the total number of elements used. Intricate contact details between yarns was facilitated using the *ERODING_SINGLE_SURFACE contact algorithm. The geometry of the fabric was modelled by sweeping a yarn cross-section along a sinusoidal centreline path in the form of Equation (11), representing the centreline trajectory of an undulated yarn, where t and s represent yarn thickness and span, respectively. Six elements were used across the yarn width to properly capture the yarn cross-section geometry. The *ERODING_SURFACE_TO_SURFACE contact algorithm was defined between yarns and the projectile. Both materials were assigned the same modulus value. UMAT has its own failure criterion as explained in Section 2.2 and erosion was implemented for *MAT_002 using *MAT_ADD_EROSION. The solver 'lsdyna.exe' was compiled using Intel Parallel Studio XE 13.1 and Visual Studio 2010 as recommended by LSTC for LS-DYNA R11.

$$y = \frac{t}{2} \cos\left(\frac{\pi x}{s}\right) \quad (11)$$

A 7.62 x 39 projectile was used for the simulation and the geometry and its mesh are illustrated in Figure 3 (a) and (b), respectively.

Figure 3: 7.62 x 39 projectile used in the simulation

A single-element uniaxial tension test for the UMAT and the *MAT_002_ORTHOTROPIC ELASTIC was performed. Subsequently, an impact simulation using a 7.62 mm x 39 projectile was carried out using both material cards at different impact velocities and the results were compared and the differences are discussed in the following section.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Single-element Uniaxial Tension Test to Failure

MAT_002 is elastic orthotropic and has a single modulus value while the dynamic modulus of the UMAT varies with strain and strain rate, according to Equation (8). To verify this property, single-element simulation of uniaxial tension was carried out at 150/s and 500/s strain rates. The results are shown in Figure 4. The black and red curves denote the behaviour of MAT_002 at 250/s and 500/s, respectively. The curves coincide, clearly exhibiting the rate independence, as expected. The green and blue curves exhibit the strain rate dependence of UMAT at 250/s and 500/s, respectively. The stress-strain response behaviour of the UMAT is hence confirmed to be rate-dependent. Subsequently, a series of impact simulations using a 7.62 x 39 projectile and a plain fabric weave was carried out using the two material models, at different velocities.

Figure 4: Stress histories of single elements at different strain rates for the two models

3.2 Ballistic Impact Simulations of Single-ply fabric Systems

Projectile defeat upon ballistic impact is essentially an energy balance between the target and the projectile. The energy (mostly kinetic) of the projectile is to be fully captured by the target, in order for the projectile to be defeated by it. Therefore, assuming the energy the projectile possesses is purely kinetic, the energy absorbed by the target can simply be expressed as shown in Equation (12). For a successful projectile defeat, $V_{residual}$ is zero.

$$E_{Absorbed} = \frac{1}{2} m_{projectile} (V_{Initial}^2 - V_{Residual}^2) \quad (12)$$

Particulars of the impact simulations and the results are tabulated in Table 1.

Table 1: Comparison of velocities and energy absorption for the two models

Impact Velocity (m/s)	Residual Velocity (m/s)		Percentage Difference in Absorbed Energy
	UMAT	MAT_002	
30	21	16	41.2
40	34	31.5	14.2
50	41	35	27.1
100	97.4	96.7	1.4
200	198.7	197.8	0.9
300	299	298.6	0.3

Analysis of the residual velocities of the single-ply impact simulation reveals that the results both in terms of residual velocities and energy absorption is significant at low-velocities. The difference is almost negligible at high impact velocities. However, typically at large impact speeds the resistance to perforation is dominated by the material mass (density) while at low impact speed the strength of the material is dominant. Since the assigned mass density of both of the models is the same, the energy difference tends to be negligible at high impact velocities. This has essentially become a loophole in numerical model validations, since high-velocity impact data can alone be used to validate a numerical model, even though the model may not represent the actual scenario at lower velocity impacts. However, the accurate material response at low velocities is very critical in simulations regarding multi-layered fabric armour systems. In multi-layered arrangements, even though the layers close to the impacting face experience very high strain rates, the layers towards the opposite end will experience low velocities

since the projectile is progressively decelerated through the system thickness. Therefore, it is critical that the material response is captured accurately over a complete range of impact velocities/strain rates.

Areas under the curves shown in Figure 4 also correlate to the energy absorbed. In the strain rates considered in this study, it can be seen that the area under the curves for MAT_002 are higher than those of the UMAT. This would generally imply that models using MAT_002 in this velocity range will show more resistance to penetration than those using the UMAT. It is clearly reflected in the residual velocities shown in Table 1. The von-Mises stress distributions and the deformation profiles of the fabric models just before penetration are shown in Figure 5 and 6, respectively.

Figure 5: von-Mises stress distributions of (a) MAT_002 and (b) UMAT.

Figure 6: Deformation profiles of the fabric models for (a) MAT_002 and (b) UMAT.

Analysis of Figures 6 and 7 reveals that the stresses generated are higher for the UMAT while its deformation in the direction of the projectile velocity is lesser than that of MAT_002.

4 Conclusions and Recommendations

In numerical modelling of high-performance fabrics, the most commonly used constitutive models are orthotropic elastic or transversely isotropic and inherently rate-independent. High-performance textile fibres, generally used in ballistic fabrics, are, however, viscoelastic in nature and therefore, rate-dependent. This study proposes the suitability of using mechano-rheological constitutive models to capture the above property. The means of implementing mechano-rheological constitutive models using the advanced *USER_DEFINED_MATERIAL_MODELS in LS-DYNA is described.

Current state-of-the-art fabric models are of the meso-scale resolution (homogenised yarn level) and hence do not account for fibre/filament details. However, progressive damage failure of elements can impart partial failure of homogenised yarns, thereby accounting for individual fibre/filament failures. However, using a single failure criterion, should it be stress- or strain-based may not be representative of a large strain rate range. Therefore, progressive damage failure with multiple failure criteria are recommended. The implementation of such codes into UMATs, could, however, be complex.

Significant differences in using a rate-dependent constitutive model was observed, rather than using a rate-independent model. The case of LS-DYNA's MAT_002-ORTHOTROPIC ELASTIC was considered as a case study in this paper. It is the most widely used constitutive material model used to represent high-performance fabrics in numerical simulations. However, it is concluded that the usage of such material models is not representative of the true material response over a range of strain rates.

The use of mechano-rheological constitutive models is worthwhile instead. However, the lack of test data over ranges of strain rates is a major deterrent in implementing such models.

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